

High Temperature Hybrid Titanium Composite Laminates: An Early Analytical Assessment

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a new type of material system that shows great promise for aerospace applications. The concept consists of thin sheets of titanium bonded together with a polymer composite prepreg consisting of a high temperature resin reinforced with high or intermediate modulus fibers. The potential material performance is outstanding from an in-plane fatigue and fracture consideration. As with all composite materials, the exact moduli and strength can be optimized for a given application by varying the constituents, their volume fractions and, in the case of the reinforcing fibers, their orientation. The paper includes analytical studies as well as experimental results.

INTRODUCTION

Traditional polymeric matrix composites (PMC's) reinforced with high modulus carbon fibers have exhibited high stiffness to weight performance as well as superior fatigue resistance when compared to traditional metallic alloys. However, due to the nature of the polymeric matrix some properties, such as bolt bearing capacity and lightning strike protection, are not as good as traditional metallics. Bolt bearing and interlaminar strength in particular can suffer at elevated temperatures. The purpose of this paper is to present a new concept for making a high temperature titanium hybrid composite laminate. A schematic of such a laminate is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. - Schematic of Hybrid Titanium Composite Laminate (HTCL)

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This hybrid laminate will be composed of thin sheets of titanium adhesively bonded together with a high temperature polymer resin that contains high or intermediate modulus fibers. As will be discussed, these laminates have the potential to offer the best points of both metallics and PMC's.

Future aircraft, both military and commercial, are being designed to reach higher speeds and be more durable than ever before. To meet the design criteria of such aircraft, the structural materials must be capable of extended use at elevated temperature while exhibiting improved damage resistance and damage tolerance. The hybrid titanium composite laminate shows promise in addressing these criteria by utilizing not only improved materials but the mechanics of lamination.

In the mid 1960's Kaufman [1] showed that the fracture toughness of adhesively laminated aluminum plies was improved in comparison to that of an equivalent monolithic plate due to the individual plies failing in a plane stress state. In the mid 70's Johnson and colleagues [2, 3] showed that significant improvements in fatigue and crack growth resistance could also be realized by adhesively laminating thin aluminum plies together. In the early 80's Johnson [4] extended this work to show that adhesively laminated titanium plies improved fracture toughness by almost 40%, increased fatigue life by an order of magnitude, and slowed down through-the-thickness crack growth rates by 20%. In the mid 80's researchers at Delft University and Alcoa developed ARALL (Aramid Reinforced Aluminum Laminates) where not only were thin plies of aluminum adhesively laminated together, but aramid fibers were also included in the bondline [5, 6]. The inclusion of the fibers offered even more improvement in mechanical behavior of the laminate, primarily due to reductions in crack growth rates resulting from a fiber bridging phenomenon. Some of the ARALL laminates were even prestrained so the aluminum plies were in a state of residual compression, further improving fatigue properties. Similar improvements have been offered by GLARE laminates [7] that are essentially the same concept, but glass fibers replace the aramid. Thus, the history of laminated metals has shown definite mechanical advantages that can translate to weight savings. These laminated aluminum parts are now flying on several commercial and military aircraft.

A preliminary study which built upon past experience and applied the laminated/hybrid technology to metals and adhesives capable of extended use at temperatures up to 200° C was conducted at NASA Langley Research Center [8]. Two unidirectional hybrid titanium composite laminates (HTCL) were made with different fiber volume fractions, resin layer thicknesses and resins. From the limited supply of material, the HTCL were tested quasi-statically to failure and fatigued [8]. The results were compared to each other and to an similar thickness piece of monolithic titanium to assess lamination affects. A laminate analysis code was used to predict the hybrid laminate response based upon constituent property input and to verify is applicability to model the mechanical response of this type of material system. The analytical code AGLPLY was then used to make a parametric study of the effect of varying fiber type (boron, high modulus carbon, and intermediate modulus carbon), two types of titanium, fiber volume fraction, fiber lay-up and the percentage of titanium to PMC.

MATERIALS

Hybrid laminates, as discussed in this paper, can be made from practically an infinite number of combination of constituents (i.e. fibers, metal plies, polymer matrix, and surface treatments.) In this study we will analytically examine the effect of several different combinations. This analytical examination will then be used to decide combinations of materials for actual fabrication and testing. Table 1 lists the constituents used in the present study and their assumed properties. Notice that each material has a reference from which these properties were obtained.

The titanium Ti-15-3 and Timetal 21S are both meta-stable beta alloys. This means that their properties, such as modulus and strength, vary significantly depending upon their heat treatment. Therefore, these properties in Table 1 are representative but could, in practice, be different.

Three different carbon fibers were examined. The IM7 was actually used to fabricate the small panels that were tested and used to verify our analysis [8]. Both IM (intermediate modulus) and HM (high modulus) fibers properties were used in the parametric study. The fibers are assumed to be linear-elastic to failure.

Only the LaRC-IA adhesive resin was used in this study. The properties of these polymer resins are so small compared to the fiber and titanium moduli that varying the resin properties would make little difference in this study. Of course the type of resin used will make a significant difference in the durability of the bonds which will profoundly effect the strength and fatigue performance of the HTCL. The effect on these properties can only be assessed by experimental testing.

Table 1. Assumed Mechanical Properties of HTCL Constituent Materials

	Ti-6-4 [8]	Timetal 21S[11]	Ti-15-3 [11]	LaRC- IA[8]	Boron [12]	Carbon HM[13]	Carbon IM7[14]	Carbon IM[15]
Long. Modulus (GPa)	118.6	116.0	91.8	3.34	385	775	275.8	213.74
Trans. Modulus (GPa)	118.6	116.0	91.8	3.34	385	6.8	13.79	13.79
Shear Modulus (GPa)	45.62	43.28	33.75	1.25	170	20.6	13.79	13.79
Long. Poisson	0.33	0.34	0.36	0.33	0.13	0.22	0.25	0.20
Trans. Poisson	0.33	0.34	0.36	0.33	0.13	0.25	0.25	0.25
Yield Strength (MPa)	827.4	910	772	71.7	---	---	---	---
Ultimate Strength (MPa)	1068.7	990	991	121.9	3850	2480	5310	3847
% Elongation	5.8	3.4	4.1	6	1.0	0.32	1.8	1.8

ANALYSIS METHOD

The AGLPLY code, developed originally to analyze metal matrix composites [9], was used to evaluate its potential for predicting the HTCL's response based on constituent input. The program performs an elastic-plastic analysis of symmetric composite laminated plates under in-plane mechanical loads. The lamina properties are calculated via the vanishing fiber diameter (VFD) model which assumes a rule of mixtures contribution of the fiber to the modulus in the longitudinal direction while offering no transverse constraint by the fiber. AGLPLY computes the overall laminate elastic moduli, the local average fiber and matrix stresses and strains in each ply as well as the overall laminate strains for the entire elastic-plastic loading regime. This program has proven successful in predicting the mechanical response of metal matrix composites in numerous studies, e.g. [9-10]. A parametric study was conducted using AGLPLY to study the effects of variations in laminate constituents. Three types of fibers and two titanium alloys were examined along with variations in the fiber volume fraction, fiber lay-up and the percentage of titanium compared to the PMC. Table 1 displays the constituent properties used to predict the composite properties.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Experimental Baseline - Miller et al.[8] made some preliminary laminates with two fiber volume fractions and two different percentages of titanium to PMC. The fiber volume fractions were measured and these approximate values were used to predict the total stress-strain curves to failure for each laminate. The results are shown in Figure 2. The AGLPLY program's predictions correlated well with the overall measured stress-strain behavior of the hybrid laminate. These predictions are based upon the mechanical properties of the constituents (fiber properties and orientation, fiber volume fraction, polymer resin properties, titanium properties, and percentage of titanium to the PMC). This good correlation gave us confidence that we could use the AGLPLY program to conduct a parametric study to assess the effect of varying the constituents. Such a study is necessary to guide the fabrication of these laminate in hopes of quickly optimizing constituent make-up for a given laminate application.

Figure 2. The AGLPLY program predictions correlate very well with the experimentally measured stress-strain curves.

Parametric Study - Many combinations of constituents in various proportions, as given in Tables 2, were analytically studied by predicting the total tensile stress-strain curve to failure. Notice that both the percentage of PMC thickness to total laminate thickness, V_{pmc} , and the volume fraction of fibers within the PMC, V_f , were varied. In this section we will describe some of the significant results of those predictions. Cross-plyed laminates were also analyzed using the same combinations of constituents but alternating 0° and 90° plies.

Table 2. Variations of HTCL constituents and volume fractions for parametric study of unidirectional laminates using LaRC-IA polymer matrix

Titanium Alloy	PMC Fiber	V_{pmc}	V_f
Timetal 21s	Boron	33%, 44%, 55%, 67%	20%, 30%, 40%, 50%
	Carbon HM	33%, 44%, 55%, 66%	40%, 50%, 60%, 70%
	Carbon IM	33%, 44%, 55%, 66%	40%, 50%, 60%, 70%
Ti-15-3	Boron	33%, 44%, 55%, 66%	20%, 30%, 40%, 50%
	Carbon HM	33%, 44%, 55%, 66%	40%, 50%, 60%, 70%
	Carbon IM	33%, 44%, 55%, 66%	40%, 50%, 60%, 70%

The stress-strain curves for the two titanium alloys (Ti-15-3 and Timetal 21S) and the LaRC- IA resin are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The stress-strain response for laminate constituents.

Effect of Fiber Type: Figure 4a presents a comparative plot of the stress strain curves to failure for laminates that all have 44% PMC (56% titanium) and 40% fiber volume fraction within the PMC layers for both titanium alloys. The laminates' failure strains are dictated by the strain to failure for their respective constituent fibers. The laminate containing the HM carbon has the highest elastic modulus as would be expected, but has the lowest strength due to the low strength as indicated in Table 1. As a matter of fact, the HM laminate fails before the polymer or the titanium yield. The laminate containing boron has a higher modulus than the intermediate modulus (IM) carbon fiber laminate. Even though the strain to failure for the boron fiber is less than the IM fibers, the ultimate strength is essentially the same. In general, one would not have an operational load above a constituent yielding, but the additional yielding and energy absorption is a positive for damage tolerance. Figure 4b is a similar plot with 55% PMC and 50% fibers in the resin layers. The trends are similar except that the laminate moduli and strengths are all higher due to the higher fiber volume fraction.

Figure 4. The relative stress-strain response as a function of fiber type and titanium. In (a.) there is a lower percentage of PMC and of fibers in the PMC than shown in (b.).

Effect of Fiber Volume Fraction: Within the scope of this analytical study, it has been shown that the higher the fiber volume fraction, the greater is the moduli and the strength. An example of such variation is shown in Figure 5 for the carbon IM fibers used with the Timetal 21S and a

PMC ratio of 44%. Fiber volume fraction using boron fibers are usually not much higher than 50% whereas carbon fibers are normally used in the 60 to 70 % range. This is an important point to be remembered when comparing the two fiber systems.

Figure 5. Variation of longitudinal moduli and strengths as a function of fiber volume fraction.

Effect of Titanium Percentage: The percentage of titanium makes for an interesting study which is beyond the scope of this paper. Relative ductility in terms of fracture toughness and crack propagation performance will be greatly influenced by the amount of titanium present, as will the bolt bearing behavior. Figure 6 shows the stress-strain response for the laminate composed of IM fibers and Timetal 21S. The fiber volume fraction is held constant while the percentage of PMC is increased from 33% to 66%. Notice the cross-over in stiffness. This occurs because the PMC with 40% IM carbon fibers has a lower modulus than the Timetal 21S. Therefore, as one increases the percentage of PMC, the modulus goes down. However, after the titanium yields, the PMC has a higher modulus; thus the greater the percentage of PMC, the higher the modulus. This was an unusual example. Basically, the PMC should always have a higher modulus than the titanium or much of the advantages of making a HTCL are lost. Typically the higher the percentage of PMC, the stiffer and stronger is the laminate. Once again this must be traded off for the previously mentioned benefits of having the metallic layers.

Figure 6. Stress-strain response for the laminate containing IM fibers with the Timetal 21S as a function of the percentage of PMC.

Effect of Fiber Orientation: As the percentage of PMC is increased, the modulus and strength are increased *in the fiber direction*. The transverse properties decrease. In most applications there is a strong presence of a dominate loading direction so this problem is acceptable. However, there are cases where a more isotropic material is required. We have examined the case of alternating 0 and 90 PMC layers between the metallic sheets. For our purposes, we assumed a 50-50 split between 0 and 90's, but, of course, this can be tailored to a given application. The case of a boron fiber PMC with Timetal 21S sheets is shown in Figure 7. For this case the percentage of PMC is 44% and the fiber volume fraction for both orientations is 50%. The stress-strain plot for the cross-ply is compared to the longitudinal and transverse stress-strain behavior of the same constituent unidirectional laminate. The cross-ply plot is the same for both the longitudinal and transverse directions. As would be expected the cross-ply properties fall in between. Also shown for completeness is the longitudinal and transverse properties of the PMC alone. Having the titanium layers make the HTCL much more isotropic than it would otherwise be using just an unidirectional PMC. The HTCL is nearly as stiff in the longitudinal direction as the PMC but is over 10 times stiffer in the transverse direction!

Figure 7. Compares the relative stiffnesses and strengths of unidirectional and cross-ply HTCL to unidirectional PMC. The fiber volume fraction is 50% for all cases.

Other Factors: Factors such as costs of constituent is important. Typically boron fibers are more expensive than carbon but may yield superior compressive properties. Thin sheets of titanium are more expensive than thicker sheets. This is important in deciding the number of layers to build-up a given thickness. The more plies, the better is the redundancy in case one ply were to fatigue.

SUMMARY

An analytical study was presented to help guide the optimization of hybrid titanium composite laminates (HTCL). Both boron and intermediate modulus carbon fibers look promising. The combination of fibers and fiber volume fraction must be such that the PMC has a higher modulus than that of the titanium in order to see significant benefits of HTCL. The higher the percentage of PMC the more attractive are the stiffness and strength properties. However, a compromise with these properties must be made in order to utilize the benefits of the metallic layers. Examples of having 90° off-axis plies were illustrated and discussed. These off-axis plies can be considered as design dictates. In general, a unidirectional HTCL is more isotropic than a typical unidirectional composite would be due the transverse contribution of the titanium layers. Studies such as this are very useful but must be combined with experimental testing to assess the effects of constituents on properties such as fatigue, fracture, durability and bolt bearing capability.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge that this work was supported by the NASA sponsored HiPPAC Center at Clark-Atlanta University (Grant Number NAGW-2939). Miller acknowledges the support of the National Research Council.

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